

POINT OF VIEW AND PASSWORD STRENGTHS

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Abstract

Many times when password authentications are breached, the authentication service is not at fault, but rather, the insecure password itself created by the user. Many sign-up pages encourage users to create strong passwords, yet they still seem to be ignored. This study attempts to analyze one potential strategy on influencing people to create stronger passwords, which delves between the subfields of cybersecurity and human-computer interaction. Visual nudges, such as password strength meters on a sign-up page, have been examined already. So instead, we take a look at potential reading nudges. This research experiment revolves around a survey, where participants are unknowingly divided into one of three groups that structure questions on a certain point of view: first, third, or none. There, participants will be asked 5 simple, free response cybersecurity questions written in the point of view that they were assigned. Afterwards, they will be asked to create a fake account to store their information. Our question is to see if roleplaying as a cybersecurity expert will affect the strength of password creations. The results seem to point to a potential conclusion that the first point of view influenced people to create stronger passwords by a considerable margin versus the third and no point of views. However, an experiment like this will need to undergo survey changes and many more trials in order to fully solidify this conclusion.

INTRODUCTION

Data breaches in 2021 reached an all-time high, with a 68% increase to a total of 1862 compared to 2020¹. Passwords play a critical part in the line of defense that prevents data breaches. However, many people do not see passwords with that much importance. They view passwords as another frustrating thing to memorize. With the many passwords an average user memorizes for their many accounts, it is to no one's surprise that users create simple passwords, and even uses the same password for multiple accounts. According to a Google survey, approximately 25% of Americans admit to having easy-to-crack passwords such as "abc123", "qwerty", "admin", and other variations². Many signup pages encourage users to create strong passwords, yet they still seemed to be ignored. More research is looking into how to get users to create stronger passwords. One solution is to use a password manager because it allows the user to create one password to unlock their other passwords. Another solution that is gaining some traction is visual nudges. Visual nudges are a psychological phenomenon that when a human views a certain thing, they get "nudged" into doing something, whether consciously or unconsciously. In context to cybersecurity, the visual nudges' goal is to display something to the user that will get them more likely to create stronger passwords. One such example is the use of colors and emoticons. As a user creates a password, different colors and emoticons are shown in real time so as to display the password's strength. A green bar and smiling emoticon would be shown if the password is strong and a red bar and sad emoticon would be shown if the password is weak. Utilizing these visual nudges attempt to persuade the user to create stronger passwords through the use of color symbolism and human emotion visualization. Visual nudges such as these have been proven to be effective. However, the point of this paper is to look for and experiment on an alternative way for users to create stronger passwords.

Instead of using an image that can be ignored, I wanted to look into the potential effectiveness of reading nudges instead. Similar to visual nudges, reading nudges are where humans read something that “nudges” them into doing something, whether consciously or unconsciously. In context to cybersecurity, the reading nudges’ goal is to have some text for users to read and questions to answer that causes them to more likely create stronger passwords after. This study delves into the possible relationship between reading nudges and password strength. However, sentences are complex, and a certain stylistic way of creating sentences may introduce a hidden bias that alters results. Instead of avoiding this bias, the goal of this paper is to focus on one of them. More specifically, one type of style for creating sentences is perspective. Perspective is a critical aspect of writing, so I focused on it as this project. Does answering cybersecurity questions structured in a certain point of view lead to the creation of stronger passwords?

I want to see if this point of view manipulation in the cybersecurity questions can alter the strength of passwords. There are three points of view that I examined: first, third, and none. The first person is where users pretend to be a cybersecurity expert and answer cybersecurity questions in the format, “What should I do?”. This point of view encourages a roleplay mindset for the reader. The third person is where users read about a cybersecurity expert and answer cybersecurity questions that decide the expert’s next move. This point of view may not be as engaging as the first point of view, but still invites the reader to the same story as an outsider. The no point of view is where users are asked cybersecurity questions from nobody’s perspective in the format, “What is the best choice?”. This is the least engaging point of view but also functions as the control group by calculating the effectiveness of the first and third points of view and comparing it to the no point of view.

The hypothesis to this experiment is that the first point of view would be the most effective at creating stronger passwords.

METHOD

The experiment revolves around an online Qualtrics survey where users will be exposed to reading nudges. Afterwards, they will create a new fake account. Passwords will be analyzed and categorized based on their strength. There are two parts to this survey: answering free response cybersecurity questions and inputting a new username and password. However, participants are only told that the focus of this experiment is to learn more about what the general public know about cybersecurity. This deception is to prevent users from learning the true purpose of this survey and altering the results due to it. Participants are told on the true nature of this experiment at the end.

The first section of the survey is where users answer five basic free response cybersecurity question. The following numbered list represents the gist of each question, with the answers being in parentheses.

- 1) The last time login authentication was changed was three years ago. How can this problem be solved? (Update the software)
- 2) Confidential network traffic data is being sent in a plaintext format. How can this be more secure? (Encrypt the data)
- 3) There is only one copy of critical data. What should be done in case the only copy of data gets corrupted? (Create data backups)
- 4) Employees keep on falling for phishing links. What is a solution to this problem? (Teach employees about phishing)

- 5) All employees have default access to all data within the business, including critical. What is a more secure alternative to this? (Have employees only have access to the data they need)

Participants are unknowingly divided into three groups. Each group stylistically rewords the same questions to the point of view group they get assigned to (first, third, or none). For the first and third point of view groups, a short introduction is provided that helps participants get into the desired mental state. For the first point of view group, participants are told to roleplay as a cybersecurity expert that graduated from a prestigious school and has many years of career experience. They are told that they will now be helping a business with their cybersecurity issues. For the third point of view group, they are told about a cybersecurity expert, with the same prestigious and experienced background, that will help a business with their cybersecurity issues. It is the participant's job to figure out what this expert will do. The no point of view group does not need an introduction. After the appropriate introduction, all groups are asked five free response cybersecurity questions that are stylistically structured on their point of view group. An example of one question being reworded to reflect a certain point of view is shown in Figure 1 below. The question in Figure 1 represents question 1) from the numbered list above.

After finishing the questions, participants are told that the main part of the survey is over, but that there is one more part to complete. This second section is where participants are told to create a fake account to store their answers. Here, they simply input a username and password. Afterwards, they are told that the survey is complete, and they are free to leave.

First Person

1) One local business hires me to check their cybersecurity measures in place. I will first start by looking at their website security. Their website security itself is decent but I see why it could be better: I notice that the last time the software that handles login authentication was updated was 3 years ago. So I will start off by...

Third Person

1) One local business hires McCarthy to check their cybersecurity measures placed. First he will check their website. The website security itself is decent but he sees why it could be better: He notices that the last time the software that handles login authentication was updated was 3 years ago. In order to fix this problem, he will...

No POV

1) There is a local business looking to improve their cyber security. First is to check the website's security. The last time the software that handles login authentication was updated was 3 years ago. What is the solution to fix this problem?

FIGURE 1. One question restyled in the three points of view.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For this experiment, 50 people were surveyed. The participants' passwords were analyzed in respect to their point of view group. Three pie graphs were created to display this analysis, which are shown below in Figures 2, 3, and 4. Each color within each pie graph represents password strength: blue for exception, green for sufficient, yellow for warning, and red for failure. Passwords that are categorized as blue and green are considered acceptable while yellow and red passwords are not. Password strength was calculated from a website provided by the University of Illinois at Chicago³. The calculator takes multiple factors into consideration such as number of characters, numbers, and symbols as well as checking for any repeats and numerical increments. Now, the graphs will be explained.

FIGURE 2. Password strength distribution of the first point of view group.

FIGURE 3. Password strength distribution of the third point of view group.

FIGURE 4. Password strength distribution of the no point of view group.

Starting with the first point of view group pie graph (Figure 2), 75% of passwords are considered to be acceptable, which make up 9 people. 25% of passwords are not considered to be acceptable, which make up 3 people.

Moving on to the third point of view group pie graph (Figure 3), 46% of passwords are considered to be acceptable, which make up 6 people. 54% of passwords are not considered to be acceptable, which make up 7 people.

In the no point of view group pie graph (Figure 4), 56% of passwords are considered to be acceptable, which make up 9 people. 44% of passwords are not considered to be acceptable, which make up 7 people.

It is obvious to tell that the first point of view group had the highest percentage of acceptable passwords, 75%. The third point of view group had the lowest, 46%. The no point of view group beat the third point of view group by a slight margin of 10%. Compared to the control group, which has been defined as the no point of view group, it seems that the first point of view group was noticeably the most effective at leading people to create stronger passwords. Roleplaying, through the usage of first-person terminology, seems to have a short, but noticeable impact on the mind. This roleplay may unconsciously continue to run in the mind even after the roleplay is over. Even when told that the main survey was over, the cybersecurity expert mindset seems to have continued to the second section of the survey where participants create a fake account. With that cybersecurity expert mentality, participants were more likely to create stronger passwords because creating strong passwords is naturally what a cybersecurity expert does. However, this experiment needs work before solidifying such a conclusion.

FUTURE WORK

There are a number of improvements needed for this experiment before its results can lead to a solid conclusion. First off, this experiment needs more participants. Before concluding something about the human mind, the sample size of the experiment needs to be greater than 50. Another improvement is to have participants memorize the password they created for a week. After a week, they would be asked to input their password to see if it is correct. Participants would also answer how they memorized their password, like using a password manager or their brain. This solves the issue of participants creating a gibberish, but coincidentally strong password as they would not need to remember it. Finally, a few participants mentioned that they would have preferred multiple choice options because they did not know how to answer certain questions. Thus, a multiple-choice version of the survey would be implemented next time.

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